

Punjab/Delhi, India

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Entry tags: Hinduism, Buddhist Traditions, Religious Group, Indic Religious Traditions, Indian Buddhist Traditions

Punjab region, India.

Date Range: 250 BCE - 1200 CE

Region: Punjab Region through Uttar Pradesh, India

Region tags: South Asia, India, Punjab, Delhi, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh

28.5-32 degrees North, 74-77.5 degrees East.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Size and Structure

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhism-There exist Ashokan edicts erected in this area during this period that indicate some degree of Buddhism practice and institutional support. As these edicts may have been connected to monastery infrastructure, this would imply some degree of established religious authority. Appears to be a mixture of religious specialists, elite patrons, and potentially less elite popular participation.

– Yes

Notes: Hinduism-Yes, religious specialists. There remains a question of the degree of integration of the non-elite in religious practice.

Beliefs

Supernatural Monitoring

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhism-Textual tradition seems to show indications of both criticisms of focus on supernatural figures and aspects of position of religious authorities (i.e., high-caste groups), yet also

shows reverence of supernatural figures potentially bestowing rewards.

– Yes

Notes: Hinduism-Commonplace element of religious texts from this period, starting with epic literature and central to Puranic literature.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhism-Given the description of the clothing (Kāṣāya) this would seem to be the case. Seemingly a marker of specialists or those who took vows.

Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: Hinduism-Ritual specialists differentiated by sacred thread (janeu).